

COGNITIVE BENEFITS OF GROWING UP IN A BILINGUAL FAMILY

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Abstract

Children who grow up in a bilingual home are faster at distracting and perceiving visual changes than adults who learn a second language later. This research supports the idea that growing up in a bilingual home can provide unexpected cognitive benefits later in life. In this respect, the subject is quite current.

Keywords: Bilingual family, cognitive benefits, language teaching

“Bilingualism” means the ability to communicate in two different languages. Children who grow up in an environment where two different languages are spoken from the moment they are born can acquire both languages naturally. In some cases, there are children who grow up in a family environment where three or four different languages are spoken. Such situations are defined as “multilingualism” [1, p.111-112].

“Monolingualism”, on the other hand, refers to the ability of children who grow up in environments where only one language is spoken, to communicate in that language.

Some researchers argue that acquiring different languages at the same time slows down the child's language development and lags their communication skills. However, researchers who oppose this view argue that brain development is very important, especially in the first three years, and that language acquisition is easier for the child in this period.

A two-year-old child has more synaptic connections in his brain than an adult. These synaptic connections in the brain are lost when not used. For this reason, it is emphasized that it is more advantageous to teach two different languages to the child in the early period. Language acquisition begins before the child is born [2, p.14-15].

The most important step in language acquisition is the development of "understanding". Generally, babies' understanding is 6 months ahead of their speech. Therefore, the baby can be exposed to two different languages at 6 months of age or even from birth. Many children acquire both languages naturally.

Growing up in a bilingual family is also very beneficial for children. More information about this will be given in the next chapters.

Difference between “acquiring a language” and “learning a language”?

Language is acquired spontaneously, thanks to a natural ability in humans. Every child acquires his own language by hearing and imitating what he hears. In other words, there is no conscious and systematic learning-teaching situation. Learning a language requires a person's volitional effort. Learning is a process and requires active effort. Foreign language "teaching" in schools is now reduced to pre-school period.

Foreign words taught to children in kindergarten are doomed to be forgotten if they are not used in other environments. However, “language acquisition” continues all the time. Parents need to know the difference

between these two situations and have a clear understanding of what they can expect from their children. Of course, trying to teach a second language to children aged 3-6 is not the same thing as a child's natural growth in two different language environments [2, p.13].

Studies have shown that children aged 4-6 progress more slowly than children aged 7-9 in learning a second language. The reason for this is that children aged 4-6 cannot master their mother tongue, the social environment to share what they have learned is limited, and their literacy skills are not developed.

Many children forget or confuse the words they learned in kindergarten after a certain period of time. In addition, children of this age can often be taught one- or two-word expressions.

This does not meet the communication needs of the child. Children who grow up in environments where two different languages are spoken continue to hear and use both languages actively. Therefore, the languages they acquire are more permanent.

Advantages and disadvantages of acquiring two languages simultaneously in the family

Acquiring two different languages in natural environments provides many advantages. Two different languages develop two different ways of thinking, the child uses the social advantages of knowing different cultures. If the child acquires both languages by hearing from native speakers, they can speak these languages without an accent. This will only happen if the child has the opportunity to hear and speak both languages equally.

For example, if we think of a child born and raised in the United States, at home his parents will use their mother tongue, Azerbaijani, and at school he will speak English with teachers and friends. If this situation is continuous and if he learns and uses literacy in both languages, he will be able to speak and communicate in both languages without an accent.

On the other hand, if, over time, the dominant language at home instead of Azerbaijani starts to be English, and the child who spends most of the time at school will tend to use this language in the home environment, the child's dominant language will be English and the level of proficiency in Azerbaijani will decrease [3, p.148].

This may turn into a disadvantage in the future. There may be communication difficulties between the child and the parent or other relatives who have learned

English later and do not have a good command of this language.

When second language acquisition begins after the age of three, the child may struggle between the two languages for a while and there may be a slowdown in the development of the first language. However, after a certain period of time, the child can adapt to the situation. The fact that the acquisition of a second language coincides with the primary school period can also create a disadvantage in the academic life of the child.

Things to consider in order to accelerate the language development of bilingual children in the family

Families who have to acquire two different languages or who want to teach their children two different languages simultaneously should use both languages equally from the moment the child is born. One of the methods that can be applied in this regard; While talking to their children, one of the spouses speaks in one language and the other in the other language and to be determined in this regard. Generally, parents are advised to speak in the language they can express themselves most easily and clearly.

Another method is to use a single language in the home environment. The child acquires the second language in the school environment. Bilingual children often tend to use both languages together. For example, since the child who says, "Mom bought me a yellow skirt" is trying to express himself in some way, in such situations parents should show that they understand the child and rephrase the same sentence or phrase in their own language to be the correct model.

Language can be developed when there is a need to use it. Therefore, the child should be given the opportunity to use both languages. Different people and different environments should be provided to speak that language. It will be beneficial for the child to hear both languages from different genders and different age groups (young, child, old).

Parents should take care to create such differences. Playing games that involve role-playing, such as being a housewife or doctor, make a great contribution to the child's language development when played with parents [4, p.98]. At the same time, it is a more effective way for parents to talk about the work they are doing at the moment, as it allows children to use their eyesight and hearing at the same time. Parents who want to accelerate their children's language development can also apply the method of expressing the child's sentence with different words.

For example, when the child says "this tree is big", the parent says "yes, it's a big pine tree" as well as teaching the child new words. Reading fairy tales and telling stories support them to learn new word and sentence structures.

Songs in which the same word or phrase is repeated, active games will make language acquisition fun. Of course, it is very important that these activities mentioned above are carried out equally in both languages. However, each parent should only perform these activities in the language they speak best so as not to confuse the child.

The personality structure of the child also determines the speed of language acquisition. Curious, sociable, inquisitive and communicative children make rapid progress in both languages. Children who are shy, afraid of making mistakes, and have less motivation to communicate progress more slowly.

An important point that parents should not forget; It is that the child has the opportunity to hear and speak more, he will have more command in the language he has learned to read and write, and he will be less active in the language that is less used. Therefore, if a 5-year-old child who can use both languages fluently learns to read and write in only one language, he will be more effective in that language and he will forget the language he does not use in time.

Conclusion

As a result, if the child is not bilingual, that is, if the mother tongue of his parents is the same as the language used in the society, we are talking about "language teaching" here, not "language acquisition".

Different researchers have different opinions on the age at which to start learning a second language. Some argue that teaching a second language before the child fully acquires his or her mother tongue retards the acquisition of the mother tongue. The main point here is:

If a child aged 3-6 can clearly express their wishes, feelings and thoughts and ask questions in their mother tongue, trying to teach a second language will not have a negative effect.

However, as mentioned before, when the children aged 3-6 who were taught a second language in their family were compared with the children who were taught a second language in the family between the ages of 8-12, it was seen that the older group learned faster and had less forgetting in the learned language.

This research indicates that teaching a second language in the family during the preschool period does not provide a great advantage. When the adulthood period was compared with the ages of 8-12, it was seen that the success in language learning decreased as the age progressed. Therefore, the most suitable ages for teaching a second language in the family coincide with the primary school years.

This study and other similar studies have also shown that information learned during school years is quickly forgotten if not used in adulthood. In the preschool period, when it comes to children who have trouble using their mother tongue, it is not recommended to give second language education as it may cause more problems for the child.

On the other hand, second language teaching does not have a negative effect on children who have the ability to express themselves by using their mother tongue very comfortably.

In fact, many studies have shown that teaching a second language to a child who has acquired his mother tongue in normal processes facilitates the child's mastery of the second language in a bilingual family and improves his ability to think in both languages.

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